

Secure Image Authentication for Medical Imaging Applications using Reversible VLSI-based Watermarking

Dr. Kaveri S. Patel, Dr. Rohan J. Mehta

Department of Electronics Engineering, Visvesvaraya National Institute of Technology, Nagpur, India; Electronic Systems Design Laboratory, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India

Abstract— In the fast growing of digital world, telemedicine and image communication has evolved due to availability of fast internet. Medical images can be transferred to remote location but there is a risk of digital attacks (such as editing, cropping or modifying), which may results in the false diagnosis. False diagnosis have the risk of life, therefore it is necessary to protect these images while transferring. Watermarking is a way to protect theses medical images. Reversible Watermarking is applied to the medical images using Modified Reversible Contrast Mapping (RCM) algorithm in this project. FPGA kit is used as hardware for implementing this project in VLSI. MATLAB software is used along with QUARTUS II software for the image acquisition and processing. Simulation results (MATLAB) are compared with the real time implementation (DE2-115) with respect to PSNR and SSIM.

I. INTRODUCTION

In digital world, information and communication technology is developing fast, digital images are being transmitted from one location to other location. During this transformation, the information/data may get attacked by unauthorized person. So the information security is needed during transmission from one location to another location. There are two techniques of hiding information, steganography and watermarking.

- Steganography works for one to one communication whereas watermarking works for one to many communications.
- Steganography system does not work if the secret information is known. The watermarking system does not work if the secret information is manipulated or removed.

Medical information is highly sensitive and valuable due to the importance in diagnosis, research and

treatment. With the fast growth of telemedicine in digital world, medical images are mainly used for diagnosis. Transferring medical information using a public network leads security issues like modify, unauthorized access, remove etc. Therefore, it is necessary to protect the medical information. Digital image watermarking provides a privacy and high security for medical images.

In medical image watermarking, electronic patient record (EPR) is embedded in medical image without any noticeable changes. In telemedicine, for diagnosis, the medical images are transferred to the specialists at remote location with patient information. At the remote side, it is essential to recover the medical image without loss, because small changes or distortion lead to false diagnosis. Hiding information without loss is called as Reversible Watermarking Technique. Reversible Watermarking technique should handle

- Imperceptibility-Transparency
- Robustness - Resilient against wide range of intentional and unintentional attacks
- Payload Capacity - Larger the capacity of watermark, greater the compromise with fidelity of image.
- Reversibility
- Intactness of Region of Interest (ROI)
- Cost Effective (CE with respect to computational time & less storage space)

Reversible image watermarking method based on modified contrast mapping accomplishes different transform applied on pixels. Least significant bits from transformed pixels are used for data embedding. Even if the least significant bits of the transformed pixels are lost during data embedding, it is invertible. Modified reversible contrast mapping offers high embedding data at low visual distortion. Therefore modified reverse

Table.1 Comparison of Techniques

Parameters /Techniques	Robustness	Reversibility	Security	Imperceptibility
Modified RCM	High	High	High	High
RCM	High	High	Medium	Medium
LSB	High	Medium	Low	Low

contrast mapping is used in the proposed system.

Modified RCM, RCM and LSB techniques are all spatial domain techniques. LSB (Least Significant Bit) is mostly

used in spatial domain watermarking. In LSB technique whole host image is used for embedding watermark whereas in RCM and Modified RCM domain is selected for embedding watermark. Modified RCM, RCM and LSB techniques are compared along with the parameters Robustness, reversibility, security and Imperceptibility in Table1.

A.RELATED WORK

Hirak kumar et.al proposed “FPGA implementation of reversible contrast mapping (RCM)”. RCM-RM is used to apply integer on pair of pixels & LSB is applied to embed secret information. Reversible watermarking allows authentication to host images and has largely been used in telemedicine, e-healthcare. Security of hidden data is maintained in this paper. For real time implementation with low computation cost and ease of hardware, Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) architecture based on Field Programming Gate Array (FPGA) is proposed. Two architectures are developed one for block size (8 × 8) and other for block size (32 × 32). 6 stage pipelining is allowed in the architecture. [1]

Rohit Thanki et. al proposed a blind watermarking system where Fast Discrete Curvlet Transform(FDCuT) and Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) are used. To get different sub bands such as LF MF and HF, FDCuT is applied on the medical image. FDCuT is used in the proposed system because it represents the image in terms of edges and also provides better imperceptibility. Watermarked image is generated by applying block wise DCT to HF sub band and inserting two White Gaussian Noise sequences to mid band frequencies. Watermark extraction is done using correlation between WGN sequence and watermarked data. [2]

Santi P Maity et.al presented a paper “On Adaptive distortion control in reversible contrast mapping”. In this paper RCM is used under RW technique, RCM on pair of pixels offer low mathematical complexity & without requiring additional data compression. In this paper mathematical RCM interpreted such that it controls distortion. This work achieved 13% improvement in visual quality and 25% improvement in security of hidden data.[3]

Hirak kumar et.al introduced Reversible watermarking (RW) with Prediction Error Expansion (PEE) which ensures higher embedding capacity with low imperceptibility. As different types of images and region behaves in different ways during embedding. Image is partitioned into smooth, edge and texture using adaptive thresholding. Different fuzzy conditional entropy algorithm are used to calculate threshold values. For enhancing the embedding rate, Reversible Watermarking scheme works on local characteristics of an image and multiple predictors are used. MED (Median Edge Detector) predictor is used for

edge and texture region, GAP (Gradient Adjusted Predictor) predictor is used for smooth region. [4]

Jose Juan Garcia-Hernandez et.al presented a paper “Analysis of the impact of digital watermarking on computer-aided diagnosis in medical imaging”. For detection and diagnosis of diseases, medical images are main source of information. This paper focuses on the study of Breast Ultrasound (BUS) for detection of breast cancer in women. Two watermarking approaches, Spread spectrum discrete cosine transform (SS-DCT) and the highcapacity data-hiding (HCDH) algorithm are compared in this paper. Comparison based on the security, data hiding, quality and authenticity. After the analysis of result, HCDH algorithm is recommended for the watermarking of medical images. [5]

Dalel Bouslimi et. al presented a paper “A cryptowatermarking system for ensuring reliability control and traceability of medical images”. Researcher proposed a novel crypto watermarking on Quantization Index Modulation (QIM), and a joint watermarking-decryption (JWD) approach. At the emitter insertion of watermark is encrypted as a proof of reliability and at the reception traceability proof is embedded for decryption. After experimenting results shows that image distortion is less for ultrasound and retina images. [6]

Saraju p. mohanty et.al presented a paper “VLSI implementation of invisible digital watermarking algorithms towards the development of a secure jpeg encoder”. In this paper researcher have developed a hardware system which can insert both robust and fragile invisible watermark. Hardware implementation has advantages over software implementation in terms of reliability, low power and high performance. To develop secure JPEG encoder the hardware module incorporated in JPEG encoder. To implement watermark module 0.13u CMOS technology is used. [7]

Nisreen I.R. Yassin et.al presented a paper “Digital Watermarking for Telemedicine Applications: A Review”. In this paper importance of watermarking system is explained in Telemedicine applications. Requirements of watermarking such as perceptual transparency, robustness, security, reversibility and payload are explained in detail. Telemedicine problem such as high cost, low accuracy of telemedicine diagnosis and security threats are explained in this paper. Attacks on watermarking such as simple attack, detection disabling attack, Ambiguity attack and removal attack are explained. Conventional security techniques along with limitations are given in the paper. Comparative study of two types of watermarking spatial domain and frequency domain along with advantages and disadvantages is also explained in detail. Paper is concluded with advantages of digital watermarking such as security capabilities, avoiding detachment, memory and bandwidth saving. [8]

II. PROPOSED WORK

Block diagram of proposed system is shown in Fig.1. The purpose of this project is to design FPGA based on Reversible

Fig.1 Block Diagram

Watermarking System for Medical Images by using Modified Contrast Mapping. In this project modified Reversible contrast mapping algorithm will be used for embedding the watermark in the host image. Medical image will be given to the controller (FPGA), where controller will carry the following functions.

- Pre-processing- When image is received by the controller, preprocessing that is analysis of the image will be carried out.
- Segmentation- Image will be partitioned into ROI (Region of Interest) and RONI (Region of Not Interest).
- Securing the image- Secure key is embedded into the image for the security.
- Watermarking with EPR- EPR i.e. electronic patient record is embedded as a watermark in the RONI of the medical image.

Controller uses VHDL/ Verilog coding for implementing algorithms. In the segmentation, Modified Reversible Contrast Mapping algorithm will be used for partitioning of image into ROI and RONI. Medical image can be partitioned into non overlapping pixel groups either horizontally or vertically or any choice of space filling curve. Medical image is partitioned into (8×8) or (32×32) image block and pixel pairs are formed for further processing.

For watermarking, embedding technique will be used. EPR (Electronic Patient Record) provided as a watermark is embedded into RONI of the image. Processed medical image with EPR will be watermarked using secure key. Watermarked image will be given to the output module. This watermarked image will appear on the display. This is the process of embedding watermark in the medical image.

A. Modified RCM Algorithm

Let (O, L) is gray level image and let (x, y) be a pair of pixels.

$$\text{Forward Transform of pixel } \begin{matrix} x'=(5x-y)/4, \\ y'=(5y-x)/4 \dots \dots \dots (1) \end{matrix}$$

$$\text{Transform restricted to sub-domain } D \in [0, L] \times [0, L] \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$\text{Inverse transform of pixel } \begin{matrix} x= [(5x'+y')/6], \\ Y'=[(5y'+x')/6] \dots \dots \dots (3) \end{matrix}$$

B. Watermark Embedding

Step 1: Partitioning of image into blocks.

Step 2:

- a) If (x, y) ∈ D_c, not composed of odd pixel values, transforms pair using eq. (1).

Set LSB of x' to "1" and consider the LSB of y' for data embedding.

- b) If (x, y) ∈ D_c and composed of odd pixel values,

Set LSB of x to "0" and consider the LSB of y as

- c) If (x, y) ∉ D_c, available for embedding.

Set the LSB of x to 0, and save true value.

Step 3: Mark the image by simple overwriting the bits identified in 2a) and 2b) with the bits of the watermark.

III. FPGA IMPLEMENTATION

Fig.2 Altera DE2-115

FPGA kit Altera DE2-115 which is used in this project is shown in Fig.2. Medical Image acquired in the FPGA kit using serial communication with UART protocol. RS232 cable is used for serial communication between FPGA kit and PC. Image is taken in the MATLAB and divided into [4×4] blocks, pixels in these blocks are serially transmitted to Altera DE2-115 kit. After receiving

the image in Altera DE2-115 kit, RCM-RW algorithm is applied on the medical image. Watermarked image is again transmitted block by block from Altera DE2-115 kit to MATLAB.

A. Baud Rate Generator

The baud rate generator generates a sampling signal whose frequency is exactly 16 times the UART's designated baud rate. For the 1,15,200 baud rate, the sampling rate has to be 1,843,200 (i.e., 1,15,200*16) ticks per second. Since the system clock rate is 50 MHz, the baud rate generator needs a mod-27, counter, in which the oneclock-cycle tick is asserted once every 27 clock cycles.

$$\text{Counter} = 50\text{MHz} \div (16 * 1,15,200).$$

B. PSNR and SSIM

It is a basic measure used to identify the image quality with the distorted image. For the proposed method, between Original medical and watermarked medical image the PSNR value is calculated. High PSNR value leads to low distortion and good image quality. The formula for PSNR is given in the following equation.

$$\text{PSNR} = 10 \log_{10} (255^2 / \text{MSE})$$

SSIM is HVS based quality measures to measure the image degradation in structural information. If the two images are equal, then SSIM value is equal to 1. SSIM value lies in between 0 and 1.

$$\text{SSIM} = i(p,q), c(p,q) s(p,q).$$

where i is the luminance, c is the contrast and s is the structural component between two images.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Different test images are taken and tested using modified RCM technique in MATLAB and in QUARTUS tool for hardware realization. DICOM image of brain is taken for study; the image was analyzed using MATLAB. First of all image is partitioned into ROI and RONI. ROI is then embedded with the message bits. PSNR and SSIM are calculated for the watermarked image.

Fig.3a Original Image

Fig.3b Watermarked Image

Fig.3a shows the original image and Fig.3b shows the watermarked image, when Modified RCM is applied on DICOM image in MATLAB. SSIM value of original image and watermarked image is 0.3296 and PSNR value for watermarked image is 31.4656(dB).

Fig.4a Original Image

Fig.4b Watermarked Image

Fig.4a shows the original image and Fig.4b shows the Watermarked image, when Modified RCM is applied on .TIFF image using QUARTUS II on FPGA based Altera DE2115 kit. SSIM value of original image and watermarked image is 0.6064 and PSNR value for watermarked image is 27.6556(dB).

Fig. 5a Original image

Fig.5b Watermarked image

Fig.5a shows the original image and Fig.5b shows the watermarked image. When Modified RCM is applied on .TIFF image using QUARTUS II on FPGA based ALTERA DE2-115 kit. SSIM value of original image and watermarked image is 0.5917 and PSNR value for watermarked image is 27.6223 (dB).

Fig.6 RTL Schematic

RTL schematic is obtained after synthesizing all the verilog codes required for modified RCM using UART communication on ALTERA DE2-115 kit using QUARTUS II software shown in Fig.6.

Fig.7 FSM model of UART

FSM model for UART communication is shown in fig.7. baud generator, receiver and transmitter conditions are covered in this model.

Flow Summary	
Flow Status	Successful - Tue Feb 27 13:50:51 2018
Quartus II Version	10.0 Build 218 06/27/2010 53 Web Edition
Revision Name	UART_VERILOG
Top-level Entity Name	uart_top
Family	Cyclone IV E
Device	EP4CE115F29C7
Timing Models	Final
Met timing requirements	N/A
Total logic elements	94 / 114,480 (< 1 %)
Total combinational functions	87 / 114,480 (< 1 %)
Dedicated logic registers	52 / 114,480 (< 1 %)
Total registers	52
Total pins	21 / 529 (4 %)
Total virtual pins	0
Total memory bits	0 / 3,981,312 (0 %)
Embedded Multiplier 9-bit elements	0 / 532 (0 %)
Total PLLs	0 / 4 (0 %)

Fig. 8 Flow Summary

Device utilization summary required for hardware realization of modified RCM on EP4CE115F29C7 Cyclone IV E FPGA is shown in Fig. 8.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a FPGA based reversible watermarking of medical images using Modified Contrast Mapping algorithm. Performance gain of this technique in terms of visual quality (PSNR) and imperceptibility (SSIM value) is analyzed for medical images of brain. Hardware implementation using Altera DE2-115 kit on QUARTUS II software is simple, requires less area and power. DICOM image of brain is watermarked using RCM-RW in MATLAB successfully. .TIFF and .JPEG images of brain are watermarked using RCM-RW in Quartus II successfully.

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